

THE LEGAL RIGHTS OF CHILDREN IN NIGERIA AND THE CHILD-CENTERED APPROACH TO DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Nigeria is one of the UN-member states that signed the Convention on the Declaration of Human Rights as well as the Convention on the Rights of a Child. This led to the adoption of the Child's Right Act. The Child's Rights Act 2003 was adopted to enhance the protection of children's rights in Nigeria. Though not all the states in Nigeria have adopted the Act into their legislation, the violation of this Act is persistent in Occurrence. The current trend, however, is the paradigm shift to a child-centered approach to development. This is an approach that recognizes the child's need in policy actions and government decisions. This approach is to enable achievement of the sustainable development goals in consideration of childhood as a stage of the human development cycle. It is, therefore, a concern as to how a nation that has continuously violated and failed in implementation of the Child's Right Act can follow the trend of recognizing the need of children in policy formation for sustainable development.

Keywords *Child Rights; Child-Centered Approach; Human Right; Development*

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Introduction

Every human being including children has the right to live, access to protection, and essential needs. The right of a child is not guaranteed by the parents, because children are humans and are pioneers in their rights¹. The Convention on the Rights of the Child placed every child on fundamental human dignity and development. The convention provided the children with the rights and responsibilities suitable to the stage of development or age. The rights of the children are also an aspect of human rights; however, the recent trend is a child-centered approach to development.

The child-centered approach describes the recognition and consideration of children in different policy contexts. This approach is recently being applied in every context of sustainable development, such as teaching and learning processes, child protection, etc. This approach enhances the recognition of a child irrespective of gender, age, culture, race, and traits. It gives children the opportunity to participate actively in decision-making concerning them and their development (Morrison, 2009). It is applied as a system which recognizes children as an individual with rights to partake in making decisions about them with respect to their age and stage of development (Munro, 2011). However, according to (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017) child-centered approach to development can be defined as a rights-based policy process that identifies the importance of childhood as a critical stage of human life that demand public investment. It is an aspect of the human rights-based approach to development which is the process of human development that considers human rights standards.

United Nations Organization, the “best interest of the child” principle would appear to be the norm presently, both internationally and otherwise. A consensus on the phrase is one thing but how to actualize it, is the more important. It involves determining what is the best interest of the child in every conceivable situation, entrenchment through positive legislation, and the issue of enforcement. there may be competing or conflicting human rights interests; for instance, between children, different groups of children, and between children and adults.

More so, the fact that the best interest of the child “shall be a primary consideration” in the decision affecting the child is an indication that it will not always be the single, overriding factor to be considered⁴ but in the administration of justice, methodology with the potential to enrich operational strategies in key focus areas. It adds a missing element to present activities by enhancing the enabling environment for equitable development, and by empowering people to make their own decisions. It brings in legal tools and institutions – laws, the judiciary, and the rule of law principle- as a means to secure freedoms and human development. It is further based on the recognition that real success in tackling poverty and vulnerability requires giving the poor and vulnerable both a stake, a voice, and real protection in the societies where they live. A human rights-based approach is not only about expanding people’s choices and capabilities but above all about the empowerment of people to decide what this process of expansion should look like.

The legal rights of the Nigerian child are contained in various municipal laws and international instruments. These laws are based on certain fundamental principles relating to the promotion of human survival, prevention of harm, promotion, and sustenance of human dignity, and the enhancement of human development. These principles recognize the basic concept that the child is the foundation of the society and he or she assures its continuity. Accordingly, the survival and continuity of human society depend upon the protection, preservation, nurture, and development of the child.

However, the definition of the word ‘child’ is contained in two international Instruments namely: The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989 and the O.A.U. Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child 1991 both of which Nigeria is a signatory. Under Article II of the latter, a child means every human being below the age of 18 years. Also, under Article I of the U.N. Convention a child is every human being below the age of 18 years unless, under the law applicable to the child, a majority is attained earlier.

Nigeria adopted the Child’s Rights Act in 2003, giving legal consent to both the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child. The country’s constitution states that for international law to take effect, Nigeria’s legislature must create a national version. But as Nigeria operates

¹ <https://www.unicef.org/child-rights-convention/child-rights-why-they-matter>

a federal system of government, the law does not automatically become applicable in all of its 36 states. In terms of the constitution, children's issues are the preserve of the constituent states. Each state legislature must make the national law applicable within its territory. And only 25 of the 36 states in Nigeria have localized the Child's Rights Act.

It is, therefore, a concern on how the implementation of the child-centered approach to development in Nigeria can be effective when the child's rights have not been fully implemented in the country. The situation of a child in Nigeria is such that it contradicts what is said to be adopted in the constitution and the Child's Right Act 2003. As the world develops considering the children, Nigeria still struggles with achieving the child's rights.

The Child in Nigeria

The definition of a child in Nigeria is not certain, this is because the constitution of Nigeria does not define a child (Iguh & Nosike, 2011). A child is defined by the National Child Welfare² as anyone who is below or 12 years of age. A child in Nigeria is also anyone under eighteen years of age (NHRC, 2021)³. A person within this range of age is characterized by trust, ingeniousness, and innocence coupled with an undeveloped state of mind. The underdeveloped state of mind of a child shows the necessity that the society should be ready to accept excesses in failure and inadequacies (Ajanwachukwu, 2016).

The legal system in Nigeria is made up of customary and statutory law. The definition of a child under the customary law is based on the customs and traditions of the people. In most customs, the age of a child does not define the capacity of the child, rather, it is determined by circumstances (Okonkwo, 1980; Obilade, 1979). The circumstances under which a child is defined in the customary law are; mental capacity determined by the ability to solve problems without the guidance of an adult, sociability which is the ability to confront issues about life without the supervision of an adult (Oloko, 1986; Ayua & Okagbue, 1996). A child is also determined under the customary law are the transfer of property and authoritative position, financial independence, initiation into age grade, and marriage (Onibokun, 1986). However, the circumstances are different across the country. For instance, in Igbo custom, the child of the family is treated as a child until the death of his father⁴. The perception of age as a definition of a child in Nigeria depends on who is defining and varies according to cultural background. The lack of a comprehensive definition that is applicable throughout the nation, is an all-encompassing handicap with regard to the just application of the provisions of the law (Iguh & Nosike, 2011).

Under the Nigerian socio-cultural context, the definition of a child varies widely due to the lack of uniformity in the cultural systems. However, with regards to Section 2 of the Children and Young Persons Law of Lagos State (1973), which provides for the welfare of the young and treatment of young offenders, a child is a person under the age of fourteen (14) years while a young person is one who has attained the age of fourteen years but is under the age of seven years. The Nigerian Labor Act (1974) considers a child as a person below fifteen (15) years of age while the National Child Welfare Policy (1989) defines a child as anybody who is twelve years of age and below. This uncertainty trailing the definition of a child under the Nigeria law was finally laid to rest by Section 274 of the Childs Rights Act (2003) which defines a child as a person who has not attained the age of eighteen (18) years. It must be noted that this is in line with the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child both to which Nigeria is a signatory. In any case, it must be borne in mind that children are the most vulnerable members of any community; they are fragile, frail, innocent, naïve, defenseless, and often oblivious of danger. They are naturally incapable of enforcing their rights and usually oblivious of them.

The State of Children in Nigeria

Since the independence of Nigeria, rivalries between different groups of the population have regularly turned into violent conflicts. Despite great hope for an improvement of the overall human rights situation in Nigeria with the "inauguration of the elected government of President Olusegun Obasanjo in May 1999" (OMCT/CLEEN, 2002), the

² National Child Welfare Policy, 1989

³ National Human Rights Commission

⁴ In the case of *Owonyin v Omotosho* (1961) 1 ANLR 304 at 309, Bairamian F.J described it as "a mirror of accepted usage"

political crisis that the country faced in 1999 and the continuation of “communal conflicts” severely affected the Nigerian population, including children. Many of them have died, lost their parents, were left disabled, or were internally displaced because of these clashes. Children have also been severely affected by the economic crises faced by the country in 1999, which has led to an increase in the number of children living in poverty or extreme poverty. Among other dangerous consequences, poverty made more children live and/or work in the street and has increased their vulnerability to trafficking (OMCT/CLEEN, 2005).

Moreover, there is a severe lack of financial resources allocated to the protection and promotion of children’s rights. Consequently, mechanisms for protection and promotion of children remain “weak, uncoordinated and not in line with Nigeria’s obligations under the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child and the UN Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women” (Ladan, 2004). Although statistics differ somehow depending on the source - “Nigeria has one of the world’s worst rates of maternal and infant mortality” (UNFPA, 2004). According to the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), “more than 72 children out of every 1000 born alive die before their first birthday,” (UNFPA, 2004). HIV/AIDS virus has reached tragic dimensions and harmful traditional practices, such as forced marriage, female genital mutilation, widowhood practices, and boy preference continued to have a negative effect on the life and welfare of the girl-child. But discrimination also affects other groups of children, such as orphans, street children, disabled children, or children born out of wedlock. A large number of children also continue to be subjected to domestic violence or corporal punishment at school or in detention facilities.

According to the report by Humanium (2021)⁵, the main problems faced by children in Nigeria are;

1. Poverty: despite the rich natural resources in Nigeria, a large number of the population lives in extreme poverty especially in rural areas. The impact of poverty on the lives of children ranges from widespread malnutrition, limited educational opportunities, sickness, etc.
2. Discrimination: physically challenged children in Nigeria suffer physical and mental deficiencies due to discriminatory practices in Nigeria. Such children are denied access to some infrastructural facilities. There are no established shelters and schools to meet these children’s needs.
3. Child abuse: enforcement of discipline in Nigeria is by corporal punishment and it is widely practiced both in families and the schools.
4. Child marriage: although child marriages are against the law of Nigeria, it still occurs in some cultures and religions in Nigeria. This has a negative impact on the children as it affects their health, overall development and prevents them from exercising their rights.
5. Female Genital Mutilation: in some regions of the country female children are faced with genital mutilation. This practice is of negative impact due to lack of hygiene, expertise, infections, and hemorrhages, and lasting psychological effects.
6. Child Trafficking: children are exposed to child traffickers in Nigeria due to a lack of protection. Not less than ten children are sold and bought for prostitution daily, some are used for rituals while some are used as child-producing machines who give birth and sell their children.

The Legal Framework on a Child’s Rights

In 1989, the United Nations Member States adopted an international legal framework on children known as the “United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child”. The convention posited that “children are not objects who belong to their parents and for whom decisions are made, or adults in training, rather, they are human beings and individuals with their own rights”. The convention identified a child as one below 18 years and provides that children should be allowed to learn, grow, develop, play and thrive with dignity⁶. Since the convention, the child’s rights legal framework has been adopted by different regions and countries.

In Africa, the child’s legal framework was enacted in 1990, as the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACPF, 2013). The Charter compelled all the member states to recognize the rights, freedoms, and duties

⁵ <https://www.humanium.org/en/nigeria/>

⁶ Further readings on the convention of child’s rights can be seen on this <https://www.unicef.org/child-rights-convention/what-is-the-convention>

provided in the Charter with their constitutions and implementation processes⁷. The Charter discouraged any tradition, custom, religious or cultural practices that contradict the provision of the Charter on a child's rights, duties, and obligations⁸. Article 2 of the charter compelled States Parties to ensure jurisdiction of the convention on every child without discrimination⁹. The States Parties were also compelled to take appropriate measures in protecting children against all forms of discrimination or punishment¹⁰.

The 1999 constitution of Nigeria has no official provision for the protection of children at the federal level, until the enactment of the Child's right act 2003 (Ladan, 2004). The Child's Right Act (2003) is the law that governs the rights, duties, and responsibilities of all children in Nigeria. The Act defined the responsibilities and rights of the children as well the those of government and institutions. To ensure appropriate enforcement, the Act prescribed punishments for abuses and offenses against the Act (Akwara, et al., 2010). The Child's Rights Act is classified into survival rights, development rights, participation rights, and protection rights by Akwara, et al. (2010).

The survival rights under the Act is the children's rights to;

1. life¹¹,
2. survive and develop¹²,
3. health services¹³,
4. the dignity of the child¹⁴,
5. freedom from discrimination¹⁵.

The development rights are rights to;

1. Leisure, recreation, and cultural activities¹⁶
2. Freedom of thought, conscience, and religion¹⁷
3. Free compulsory and universal primary education¹⁸
4. Parental care, protection, and maintenance¹⁹

The participation rights are the right of the children to;

1. Freely associate and assemble peacefully²⁰
2. Free expression of oneself²¹
3. Free movement²²

⁷ Article 1 (1)

⁸ Article 1 (3)

⁹ Article 2 (1) 1. States Parties shall respect and ensure the rights set forth in the present Convention to each child within their jurisdiction without discrimination of any kind, irrespective of the child's or his or her parent's or legal guardian's race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national, ethnic or social origin, property, disability, birth or other status.

¹⁰ Article 2 (2) 2. States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that the child is protected against all forms of discrimination or punishment on the basis of the status, activities, expressed opinions, or beliefs of the child's parents, legal guardians, or family members.

¹¹ Section 3(1) Child's Rights Act 2003, Section 33 1999 Constitution

¹² Section 4 Child's Rights Act 2003.

¹³ Section 13(1) Child's Rights Act 2003.

¹⁴ Section 11 Child's Rights Act

¹⁵ Section 10 Child's Rights Act

¹⁶ Section 12 Child's Rights Act

¹⁷ Section 7 Child's Rights Act.

¹⁸ Section 15 Child's Rights Act

¹⁹ Section 14 Child's Rights Act.

²⁰ Section 6 Child's Rights Act, Section 40 1999 Constitution

²¹ Section 3 Child's Rights Act, Section 39 1999 Constitution.

²² Section 9 Child's Rights Act.

4. Personal liberty²³

The protection rights are the right of children in need of special protection²⁴ and the right of the unborn child to be protected against harm²⁵

The Child's Right Act 2003 provided all laws and matters relating to children for legal documentation. The Act made provisions for the protection of all the children in Nigeria without discrimination on gender, parental status, and political positions. It also provided the kind of punishment to be given to children in other words the process of criminal justice for children. The Child's right act 2003 generally provided laws and orders which recognized Nigerian child as other children around the world especially among countries that adopted the Convention on Rights of the Child.

Child-Centered Approach to Development

A child-centered approach to development²⁶ is the underlying method to achieving sustainable development by recognizing the crucial importance of children in decision-making and policy actions. This approach involves recognizing that childhood is an important stage in human life that requires attention (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017). The attention given to a person at this stage contributes to the potentials of the individual in sustainable development. This can be in the form of education, protection, moral upbringing, parental guidance and maintenance, emotional assistance, and all other necessities. The principal characteristic of childhood is an "undeveloped" state of mind, which requires that society accept and tolerate the shortcomings of a person at this stage of human development (Ajanwachukwu, 2016). The child-centered approach to development recognized childhood as the suitable stage to focus on in the formulation of policy. This would enhance consideration of norms and morals for human development since the global effort on child's rights has committed to appreciating the rights of children in social, political, economic, and cultural spheres of life (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017). Considering the childhood stage of human development to sustainable development addresses family and community needs which is justified on economic and social involvement that would benefit the individual and the society at large (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017). In the context of developed countries, investments in children are often seen as the most cost-effective way to break the cycle of disadvantage and promote social mobility (European Commission, 2013) or as a vehicle for strong and inclusive growth (OECD, 2016a).

The child-centered approach also involves a rights-based sustainable development method that acknowledges the impact of all policy actions on the well-being of a person at the childhood stage (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017). According to Licari, et al. (2005) certain policy actions affect children's well-being. They affect the biological make-up of a child in the sense that developing organisms are fragile and susceptible to various chemical and physical agents. Rapid growth and development of the organs are vulnerable and critically susceptible. Exposing children to external agents at the childhood stage of development may affect the health adversely which can result in issues such as birth defects and neurodevelopmental damage. Certain policy actions also affect the social, economic, and psychological make-up of a child. The economic and social status of children exposes them to the various environmental threat which can affect their health in the future. These factors primarily include economic and social status, which can carry their effects into adult life (Smith et al., 1997; Gunnell et al., 1998). The interaction of these factors such as educational background, location of residence, gender, ethnicity, and the knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of parents, teachers, and peers, influences exposure and risks and, as a consequence, different and possibly cumulative health effects. Age locates an individual within a social structure (Elder and Rockwell, 1979), which affects evolving opportunities, risks, and constraints. The timing of public action over the human life cycle determines the extent of individual outcomes and, consequently, the effectiveness of public investments. It is non-controversial to say that

²³ Section 180, 245 Child's Rights Act, Section 55 1999 Constitution

²⁴ section 16(1) Child's Rights Act

²⁵ Section 17(1) Child's Rights Act.

²⁶ Further reading on Child-centred Approach to Sustainable Development Goals in High-income Countries: Conceptual Issues and Monitoring Approaches from UNICEF office of Research Innocenti by Zlata Bruckauf and Sarah Cook

the well-being of children today translates into the well-being of adults tomorrow. This is because prevention or 'front-loading' strategies ensure effectiveness and higher returns on public investment (OECD, 2009, 2015).

Another aspect of the child-centered approach to development is assessing the progress of sustainable development goals of a country in the context of child rights and other relevant indicators as well as children's voices and participation in the process of social and civic development (Bruchauf & Cook, 2017). Childhood is a time of rapid development, increased risks, and also enormous opportunities. A wealth of evidence suggests that public returns on investments in children are high, particularly when policy ensures that the most disadvantaged children are benefiting from the provision (Sylva et al., 2004; Heckman, 2006; Rees et al., 2012). The rationale of putting children at the heart of the SDG agenda also includes practical considerations that reflect a growing demand to monitor how children in rich and poor countries are doing within a multidimensional, child-specific framework (Richardson et al., 2017). Immediate concerns of economic capacity, environmental sustainability, and social progress can be debated and addressed in terms of the general population. Yet, the overriding equity and equality agenda of SDGs is inseparable from the concerns about how society treats, supports, and includes children and young people in the community over the next fifteen years or so. By focusing on the well-being of children and the opportunities available to them in society, SDG policy efforts will allow governments to achieve many SDG targets faster and in more cost-efficient ways.

Implementation of Child's Right Act 2003 and the trend of Child-centered Approach to Development in Nigeria

Nigeria is a federation of 36 autonomous states. The Nigerian constitution²⁷ supports the legislative system in each state, that is to say, that the Child's Right Act 2003 is not compelled on the states rather it is a decision by the states to adopt the Act or not (Akinwumi, 2010). As a result, persecution of violations of the Child Rights Act by a court cannot be done in states that have not enacted it. Implementation of Child Rights is dependent on the legislator's decision in a state. That is why in most Nigerian states, children are faced with abuses of early marriage²⁸, child trafficking, prostitution, and several forms of discrimination. The implementation of child rights in Nigeria cannot be fully implemented without special force on the states. However, Nigeria is recognized to have legal obligations in Child Rights as a member of the UN. "Nigeria has not only failed to ratify the Child Rights Convention but has also failed in making a serious commitment to the letter or the spirit of the Convention" (Akinwumi, 2010).

The child Rights Act has been adopted by 24 of the 36 states in Nigeria (Opeloye, 2016) The National Child Rights Implementation Committee was created at the national and state level to provide solutions to challenges facing the implementation of the Act. They were keen to empowering women so that they can cater to their children, creating safe water supply and sanitation, sensitization on HIV/ AIDs, providing access to universal basic education, creation of a primary health care system among others (United Nations, 2010). However, it was reported that the activities of this committee in enforcing the implementation of the Child's Right Act were low. Also, Akinwumi (2010) noted that the Child's Right Act contradicts the Young person's Acts in Nigeria; the former identifies a child as one below 18 years, the latter sees a child as one below 14 years. The separate definitions of a child pose issue to the interpretation of a child in the legal system (Akinwumi, 2010).

The major challenge to the implementation of the Child Rights Act 2003 is the ignorant of the people on the rights of children in the country. Educating the citizens on the Child's Rights Convention and the human rights of every individual can be an effective way to encourage the implementation of the child's rights in Nigeria. According to Akinwumi, (2010), Nigeria as a member state of the United Nations and has signed the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights is compelled to enforce protection of child's rights in the country, but this has not been achieved. It is the duty of the Nigerian government to educate the citizens on the rights of a child in global terms and national terms.

The right of a child is no longer a current trend across the globe because it is assumed to be an achieved agenda in many countries. The current trend, however, is the recognition of children's needs in achieving the sustainable development goal. This is because protection and promotion of the rights of the child safeguard a future for such a

²⁷ See 1999 Nigerian Constitution

²⁸ Early marriage is mainly seen among the Muslim religious in the north. It is an accepted practice in the religion, efforts to stop the practice proved abortive in Nigeria.

child as well as the nation at large, and the way the rights of a child are recognized reduces the challenges that retards the childhood stage of human development. The concern is how a nation that has not abided by the laws of the Child's Rights Act can achieve sustainable development through the Child-centered approach. The implication is that the future of Nigeria is at risk because the children whose rights are been violated today would be in charge of the nation tomorrow. If the effects of these violations on the children are not considered today, the future is at stake.

Conclusions

Child's Rights are no longer a trend in global issues because it is assumed to have been achieved. Nonetheless, the children in Nigeria are said to face different hazardous situations such as child marriage, female genital mutilation, child trafficking, child labor, etc. which in essence contradicts the Act. Nigeria adopted the Child's Right Act in 2003 to enhance the protection of the children's rights, however, the implementation is reported to be very low and the violation is a steady occurrence. Currently, not all the states in Nigeria have adopted the Act into their legislative system, and as such violation of the child's rights cannot be challenged in the states.

Nigeria as a federation should endeavor to enforce the implementation of the child's rights act so as to follow suit in the Child-centered approach which is the trend for achieving sustainable development. This approach puts into consideration, the needs of the children and recognizes them as the future heirs of the nation. Also, it recognized the childhood stage as a pertinent stage in human development the requires attention and public investment so as to solve persistent problems in the future. It is, therefore, essential that the implementation of the Child's Rights Act is enforced in the nation.

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